

Organizational Conflicts in the Indian Public Health Sector Because of Contractual and Regular Employment

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Abstract: This article reviews the conflict that existed within the public health sector of India because of two bases of employment viz regular and contractual. Human Resources Management (HRM) under the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) was studied during 2010-12. The two sets of employees respectively the contractual and regular were working in the same organization. Many times, they were in mutual conflict because of different terms of employment, remuneration, and control. HRM under the NRHM was having several deficiencies and this was one among many others. For authorities, it was more convenient to exert control over a contractual staff compared to regular staff. Such control was considered unwarranted, discriminatory, and unjustifiable by the contractual people. There was moderate outward migration of contractual people, leaving the organization with their experiences and skills. The employment relationship was short-lived. Authorities were ignorant of several established norms of HRM, which were not suitable for attaining public health objectives and preparedness.

KEYWORDS

1. Organizational conflict 2. Public health workforce 3. Human resources for public health. 4. Organizational control 5. HRM for NRHM 6. Employee relationship.

1. Introduction

This paper would be significant because it may lead to a unified public health cadre in India on the patterns of various other cadres at the state and central levels. I consider this as an additional contribution to the knowledge and literature in the field of human resources management (HRM) for public health. The paper is based upon a dedicated study of the HRM under the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM). The study was completed following academic research customs, traditions, and practices. A degree of empiricism applied to this study as the scholar worked as a program manager with the Jharkhand Government, who had resigned from the job prematurely.

The National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) was launched in the year 2005 by Prime Minister Manmohan Singh. Later, National Urban Health Mission (NUHM) was also launched and now both the NRHM and NUHM were brought under the aegis of the unified National Health Mission (NHM).

India was lagging on several developmental indexes related to public health. One of the main reasons was the tremendous shortage of varied public health workforce. Neither the respective state nor the central government was able to meet that required workforce in near future. Additionally, any government department or ministry usually functioned under rigid rules and regulations which was most averse to recruiting and regulating the public health workforce in adequate numbers in a short period. There may be some other hidden objectives also, however, the main objective was to arrange the required public health workforce quickly and on easy terms.

Human resources planning is basic to the success of any organization. For sake of success usually, an HR department used to remain associated with the core decision-making group of an organization. Thus, a project-based approach was adopted by the government. A project-based approach has been described by (Thiry, 2007) whereby a temporary organization is created and gets embedded with any permanent organization. The new organization thus created provide them flexibility in rules and regulations and they could hire and fire the workforce with ease. In this manner, mission directorates, and health societies were created and embedded with the existing ministry/department of health and family welfare at the national, state, district, and subdistrict levels after 2005 with the launch of the National Rural Health Mission.

Such a project-based approach was having certain advantages as well as certain disadvantages also. People recruited in the project-based organization work for a project and the moment project is completed they get relieved. They can never be a government employee even working for a government department or ministry. Thus, the employment relationship in the organization was short-lived. Outward migration, and deserting the organization were extremely high among the contractual people. They were leaving the organization with their knowledge, experience, and skill that could have been utilized by the public health organizations in attaining their objectives.

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The ideas may be novice as project managers may be asked to take a more strategic focus and, as organizational authorities would be looking for a better strategy for delivering results. Both with mitigated success, well-integrated PBOs could be a possible answer, provided their structures provide horizontal integration from strategy to operational benefits and vertical integration between objectives and the prioritized portfolio of projects. It was expected that the adoption of an integrated wide-scale project approach, including a governance-oriented PMO, would enable organizations to deliver value consistently for all their stakeholders and therefore promote the Organizational Project Management concept.

Thus, the hiring of people was not done by the permanent structure of the ministry of health, but by the mission's directorates and healthy societies. Even the hiring process was very diversified. The initial seven years of implementation of the NRHM were very successful, as there was tremendous progress in attaining core public health objectives. The Sample Registration System data (SRS, 2012), Rural Health Survey Reports (RHS, 2011), National Family Health Survey data (NFHS, 2012), and District Level Household and Facility Survey data (DLHS, 2013) established that there was a tremendous improvement in indicators relating to population health in all over India. Even the improvement for the eight Empowered Action Group (EAG) States (EAG, 2004) Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh, Orissa, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, and Uttaranchal was very impressive (CRM, 2012).

It was not so that only health departments were doing such endeavours, however, a range of government departments started recruiting people in the same manner. In this manner doctors, managers, nurses, technicians, and all range of the public health workforce were hired on a contractual basis directly by the mission directorates and health societies. Moreover, massive public health voluntarism came into existence because of the large-scale involvement of Accredited Social Health Activists, ASHA.

2. Problem

Organizational conflict, or workplace conflict, is a state of discord caused by the actual or perceived opposition of needs, values and interests between people working together (Wikipedia, 2013). Conflict is quite usual the world over because of certain types of people's behaviour. However, there was a different case scenario altogether. Two sets of employees were having different salaries, and terms of employment for even similar job assignments, having the same qualification. This was certainly discriminatory.

Same group conflict is defined as a conflict within the same cadre. A cadre is a group of people who are usually appointed by why the same employer has a very similar nature of work. However, the contractual and regular staff were not in the same cadre as still there was no cadre existed for them either at the state or the central levels. nevertheless, conflicts either formal or informal existed between the same group of people be it doctors, nurses, or lab technicians.

The conflicts were caused because of HR policies. Under the National Rural Health Mission, the policy of two sets of people working under the same organization was considered discriminatory. One set of people was appointed on a contractual basis for a limited period. Whereas another set of people was appointed regularly. The people with a contractual appointment were getting fixed remuneration as well as their period of employment was shorter with no pension or any other superannuation facilities. Their service was regulated within the premises of a contract mutually signed between the contractual staff and the employer. Both regular and contractual employees were usually doing the same kind of work and also had almost similar basic qualifications.

Usually, a conflict occurs when one party decides that the way things are not going well or there is no scope for improvement in future. Moreover, the sought change is not agreed to by the other party. It is important to realize that despite the old saying that "it takes two to tangle", in reality, it only takes one party to declare a conflict (Windle & Suzanne, 2013). Conflicts occur in organizations as a result of competition for supremacy, leadership style, scarcity of common resources, etc. (Omisore & Abiodun, 2013).

The idea of having dedicated personnel for public health management goes back to 1959 when advocated by the Mudaliar Committee, which observed that "personnel dealing with problems of health and welfare should have a comprehensive and wide outlook and rich experience of administration at the state level" (Mudaliar, 1962).

Issues started emerging from several organizations very soon after the organization adopted a project-based approach. The issues were not restricted to the health department; however, it was extended to all other government departments and organizations including education departments where several demonstrations were organized by contractual teachers demanding equal work- equal pay. Several court cases were filed by the contractual employees in different courts. The issue cannot be justified that contractual people were having a choice to enter into such contracts. In the name of choice, such arrangements cannot be justified. On one side regular employees were given 5th- 6th pay commission pay scales and contrary to that contractual employees were paid lower compared to the regular employees.

While working with the Jharkhand Government as a program manager, having the charges of 3 districts for the implementation of various health programs under NRHM, I observed that there was a significant level of discrimination against the contractual staff. For example; if there is any Primary Health centre, if there were no regular doctors then contractual doctors cannot serve as medical officers in charge because the contractual staff were not having any financial responsibilities. In such cases, the medical officer in charge (MOIC) of any adjoining Primary Health Centre (PHC) was given

the financial power of that particular PHC. In some cases, the financial power was given to even the Civil Surgeon Cum Chief Medical Officer (CMO) of that district.

The contract signed between the contractual staff and employer clearly stated that the contract would be extended further if there would be satisfactory reports for the concerned contractual staff.

3. Methods

A typical case study method inclusive of observation and interviews was adopted for this study. It also included literature surveys and empiricism. People were contacted from different work groups and different organizations. Available literature from other states and newspaper reporting were taken into consideration before making any inferences.

Findings

Under the influence of International Development practices, it has been widely seen in India that in several social and development sectors including health the government has started functioning in a project-based manner whereby a temporary organisation was created and embedded with the permanent ministry or department of the government. Such a project-based approach was adopted to achieve the objectives of the concerned department or ministry which was not possible for the permanent structure. Thus, the temporary organisation was created under the health ministry at the national, state, district and sub-district levels. All such temporary organizations had a different set of people, appointed on a contractual basis. It provided the flexibility and hence they were also able to meet the funds' crunch as contractual staff were not paid the 5th or 6th pay commission scale.

Usually, a government department works amidst rigid rules and regulations. Therefore, such new organisations got embedded in the permanent organisation of the government for being more flexible in approach. Such organizations being mostly temporary, enabled flexibility to recruit and fire employees according to their suitability needs.

The contractual staff were devoid of promotion. For example, a regular medical officer could become a medical officer in charge (MOIC), Deputy Chief Medical Officer, Civil Surgeon or Chief Medical Officer (CS Cum CMO), Regional Director, or Director in a time-bound manner. However, such promotion could not be provided to a doctor appointed on a contractual basis. This was a case for almost all types of the public health workforce. Any grievances of contractual staff were liable to be dealt with accordingly to the Indian Conciliation and Arbitration Acts. Managing Conflict in the workplace is a time-consuming but necessary task (Ramsay, 2001). Although conflicts existed between the same types of workforces also, however, the conflict between the contractual and regular staff existed even between the same workforce. For example, contractual doctors versus regular doctors, nurses, and so on. It further existed between physicians, between physicians and staff, and between the staff or the health care team and the patient or patient's family. The conflicts varied from disagreements to major controversies that may lead to litigation or even violence. Conflicts most often resulted in an adverse effect on productivity, morale, and patient care. Additionally, they further resulted in low employee turnover and restricting staff contributions and impeding efficiency.

Various types of conflicts could be easily visible at the levels of individuals, inter groups, and inter-organizations. The causes of such conflicts were mainly related to roles, responsibilities, terms of employment, and compensation. There was a high percentage of people deserting the organisation because of contractual terms and conditions. The lack of retention of contractual people was evident, if an employee moves out of an organization, he or she drains out the knowledge with him or her. It was disturbing the performance of the end outcome of several public health institutions and public health services consecutively suffered with unusual breakdown. In some cases, such a breakdown was very serious, long-lasting, and even permanent. Sometimes, such situations were life-threatening.

The public health sector was face to face with one of the unique human resource management problems. The government doctors were paid no practising allowance for not getting indulged in private medical practices, however as per my observation, and applying empiricism, I can say that not all doctors were successful in private practice as they lacked the reputation of the people. There was a limited number of doctors who were successful in attracting patients both in their private clinics as well as in the OPDs of any public health facility. There was no system for performance-based incentives, and remuneration, therefore, even the non-reputed doctor who was not able to attract patients in the OPDs were also getting non-practising allowances similar to those few reputed doctors. The public health human resources management (PH²RM) must look toward this aspect of performance-based incentives or compensation systems. Reputed and performing doctors, paramedics, or technicians must be rewarded. If there would be no distinction between a reputed and performing doctor and a non-reputed or non-performing one then the public health system would not achieve its objectives. In many places, doctors were engaged in private practice even after getting non-practising allowances. This was certainly criminal behaviour running private clinics, pathology, X-ray, and ultrasound labs just near any public health facility.

4. Conclusion

The organizational conflict in the various organizations of the National Rural Health Mission was a reality. It was contributed by people being recruited on a contractual and temporary basis. The conflict was within the same cadre and same group of people. E.g., contractual doctor versus regular doctor and contractual nurse versus regular nurse and so

on. People on a contractual basis were hired for some reason that compared to regular people contractual people could be better controlled, multitasked, multiskilled, hired and fired with ease. This was discriminatory and resulted in various litigations, court cases, desertion, and even low employee turnover in some cases.

5. Suggestions and recommendations

I would suggest and recommend as follows: -

- a) Create a permanent public health cadre at the national and state levels.
- b) Try to remunerate contractual people as much salary almost equal to those regular employees.
- c) Fix the date of retirement or superannuation just similar to the regular employees.
- d) The contract should be extended for at least ten years.
- e) Arrangements should be made for pension and other benefits on a similar basis to that of regular staff
- f) Governments should try to regularize the contractual staff
- g) The contractual staff should enjoy all the powers and responsibilities in the same manner to that as regular employees.
- h) A separate cadre may be considered for the contractual public health workforce.

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7. Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest has been declared by the sole author and principal investigator.

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